

PHYSIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE ECG

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ABSTRACT

This research paper examines the key physiological mechanisms underlying the formation of the electrocardiogram. It analyzes the characteristics of cardiomyocyte action potentials, the role of the cardiac conduction system (sinus node, atrioventricular node, His bundle, and Purkinje fibers), the relationship between electrical processes and the phases of cardiac circulation, and the patterns of the appearance of the main ECG elements—waves, segments, and intervals

There are two types of myocardial cells: cells of the conduction system and contractile cells. Specific functions of the heart: Automaticity – independent generation of electrical impulses of the conduction system of the heart.

Pacemaker cells have this function, producing impulses without external stimuli. The greatest automatism is at the sinus node (the center of first-order automatism), where impulses are generated at a frequency of 60-80 per minute at rest.

The atrioventricular connection (second-order center of automaticity) can be the source of rhythm and produce 40-60 impulses per minute. The ventricular conduction system (third-order center of automaticity) generates 20-40 impulses per minute.

Excitability – excitation under the influence of impulses of myocardial cells: contractile and conductive. Excitation of the myocardium leads to the appearance of an electric current in it, which can be recorded in the form of an electrocardiogram.

Conduction is the conduction of electrical impulses by myocardial cells from the place of their origin to the contractile cells.

The propagation of excitation in the atria occurs from the sinus node along three tracts (Bachmann, Wenckebach and Thorel) to the atrioventricular junction and the left atrium, at a speed of 1 m/s.

The delay of excitation in the atrioventricular node, at which the conduction velocity decreases to 5-20 cm/s, contributes to the sequential excitation in the ventricles occurs with acceleration: the trunk of the His bundle, its right and left branches up to 3-4 m/s, Purkinje fibers - up to 4-5 m/s. Contractility is the contraction of cardiomyocytes under the influence of impulses.

Refractoriness is the inability of excited cardiomyocytes to reactivate when exposed to an extraordinary impulse. There is absolute and relative refractoriness. With absolute

refractoriness, myocardial cells do not respond even to super-strong impulses (phases 0, 1, 2 of the transmembrane action potential, on the ECG - QRS complex and ST segment). With relative refractoriness, excitability is partially restored and the cells respond to super-strong impulses (phase 3 of the transmembrane action potential, T wave on the ECG). These two refractory periods correspond to systole.

During diastole (phase 4 of the transmembrane action potential), there is no refractoriness and cardiomyocytes are able to excite. Aberration is the pathological conduction of impulses through the atria or ventricles. An ECG allows you to study all of the above functions of the heart.

Electrocardiography is one of the key functional diagnostic methods widely used in clinical practice to assess the electrical activity of the heart.

Since Einthoven's discovery, the ECG has become an integral tool in medicine due to its ability to display minute changes in the electrophysiological processes of cardiac activity.

The ECG is based on fundamental physiological mechanisms: automaticity, conductivity, excitability and contractility of heart tissue. The physiology of the ECG reflects the work of the conduction system - the sinus node, the atrioventricular node, the His bundle and the Purkinje fibers - as well as the activity of working cardiomyocytes, ensuring coordinated contraction of the atria and ventricles. The electrical activity of the heart, recorded on the surface of the body, is the result of the total vector processes of depolarization and repolarization of millions of cells.

That is why the ECG is able to detect both gross functional disorders and subtle deviations that do not manifest themselves clinically.

An introduction to the physiology of the ECG allows us to understand why various pathological conditions - ischemia, electrolyte disturbances, inflammatory processes, stress changes - lead to specific changes in the shape, amplitude and duration of teeth, segments and intervals. Thus, the ECG is a tool that bridges fundamental physiology with clinical practice.

The basis of ECG physiology is the cardiomyocyte action potential - a dynamic change in membrane potential that occurs under the influence of sodium, potassium and calcium flows. The action potential of working cardiomyocytes includes five phases: rapid depolarization (phase 0), early repolarization (phase 1), plateau (phase 2), final repolarization (phase 3) and stable resting potential (phase 4). These phasic processes determine the shape of the ECG waves: atrial depolarization forms the P wave, ventricular depolarization forms the QRS complex, and their repolarization forms the T wave.

The work of the heart as an electrical organ begins in the sinus node - the main pacemaker, which has the unique property of automaticity. Its cells generate impulses due to slow diastolic depolarization caused by calcium and "funny" sodium currents.

This impulse spreads through the atria, which is displayed as the P wave. The atria depolarize relatively slowly, so the P wave has a smooth, rounded shape. Next, the excitation reaches the atrioventricular node, which provides a conduction delay, preventing simultaneous contraction of the atria and ventricles.

This delay is reflected in the P-R interval. Any changes in the duration of this interval indicate a violation of AV conduction, which has important diagnostic significance. The conduction system of the ventricles - the His bundle and Purkinje fibers - provides ultra-fast

impulse propagation necessary for synchronous contraction of the powerful ventricular myocardium. Electrical activation of the ventricles forms the QRS complex. Its narrow shape reflects the high rate of depolarization.

Widening of the complex is a marker of conduction disorders, hypertrophy or necrosis. After contraction of the ventricles, repolarization begins - restoration of the original charge of the membrane. This process forms the T wave, the size and shape of which are especially sensitive to electrolyte disturbances (hypo- and hyperkalemia), ischemia, and drug intoxication. Since repolarization is not simply the reverse process of depolarization, the T wave is not a mirror image of the QRS, but is formed according to its own physiological laws.

The electrical axis of the heart is another important physiological indicator, reflecting the total direction of the ventricular depolarization vector. Variations in the axis are explained by the anatomical position of the heart, the mass of the myocardium, and the characteristics of the conducted impulses.

Axis displacement may be a sign of hypertrophy, bundle branch block, or lung disease. The most important physiological aspect of the ECG is the influence of the autonomic nervous system. Sympathetic stimulation increases heart rate, increases conduction, and increases susceptibility to arrhythmias.

Parasympathetic stimulation has the opposite effect. Regulatory dynamics are reflected in changes in R-R intervals, P-R duration, and T wave morphology. Ionic processes are the foundation of electrophysiology. An increase in potassium concentration leads to a sharpening of the T wave, a decrease in P amplitude and a widening of the QRS.

Hypokalemia causes the appearance of a U-shaped wave and flattening of the T wave. Calcium primarily affects the QT interval: hypercalcemia shortens it, hypocalcemia prolongs it, increasing the risk of fatal arrhythmias. The physiology of the ECG is closely related to cardiac mechanics: depolarization of the atria precedes their contraction, the QRS complex precedes the beginning of ventricular systole, and the T wave coincides with the beginning of diastole. This strict sequence ensures consistent pumping function of the heart.

Thus, the ECG is not just a line on paper, but an accurate reflection of the physiological properties of the myocardium and conduction system. It is a highly sensitive indicator of metabolic and structural disorders, allowing pathology to be detected at the earliest stages.

Physiological aspects of the ECG represent a complex of fundamental electrophysiological patterns that determine the electrical activity of the heart. A deep understanding of the nature of the teeth, segments and intervals allows not only to diagnose diseases, but also to assess the adaptive capabilities of the body.

ECG combines the simplicity of the method and high information content, which makes it an indispensable tool of modern medicine. Physiological interpretation of the ECG is the basis for the correct analysis of arrhythmias, ischemic changes, electrolyte imbalance and conduction disorders.

The study of electrophysiological mechanisms of the heart remains a key area of fundamental physiology and clinical cardiology.

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